

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

A Conceptual Review of Dhanyaka Ghrita

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GSC Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 15(03), 063–068

Publication history: Received on 23 April 2023; revised on 02 June 2023; accepted on 04 June 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2023.15.3.0170>

Abstract:

Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals deals with various methods of preparation of medicines. *Sneha Kalpana* is one of them and it may be defined as a pharmaceutical process which prepare oleaginous medicaments by using substances like Kalka, Drava dravya i.e., Swaras, kwatha etc.in specific proportion and subjecting to a unique heating pattern and duration to fulfil certain pharmaceutical parameters. This process ensures transformation of active therapeutic properties of the ingredients to the solvents. Ghrita formulations are included under the *Sneha Kalpana*. Ghrita is considered to be best because of its unique nature of incorporating the properties of the drugs with which it comes in contact without leaving its own natural qualities. Total four references of *Dhanyaka Ghrita* are available in Vangasen Samhita. It is indicated in *Atisara, Ajirna, Amvata, Amashoola, Gudashoola, Vankshanshoola, Yonishoola, Amavata, Udavarta, Arsharaga* etc.

Keywords: *Sneha Kalpana; Dhanyaka; Dhanyaka Ghrita; Atisara; Ajirna.*

1. Introduction:

Ayurveda the science of life, uses natural resources to fulfil the fundamental objectives i.e., *Swasthya Rakshanam* and *Vyadhi prashamanam*.

स्वास्थ्यस्य स्वास्थ्य रक्षणं, आतुरस्य विकार प्रशमनं च ||¹

च.सू.30/26

Ayurveda has been given the greatest emphasis to comprehensive knowledge of the drugs. The science of manufacturing drugs is divided under two branches as *Rasashastra* and *Bhaishajya Kalpana*.

पंचविधं कषायं इति तद्यथा – स्वरसः कल्कः श्रुतः शीतः फांटः कषायः च इति ||²

च.सू.4/7

Bhaishajya Kalpana includes *Panchavidha Kashaya Kalpana – Swaras* (juice), *Kalka* (paste), *Kwatha* (decoction), *Hima* (cold infusion), *Phanta* (hot infusion). These are the basic Kalpana of all formulations explained in Ayurveda. Each Kalpana has its unique preparation and utility. The preparation like *Avaleha Kalpana* (confections), *Vati Kalpana* (tablet), *Asava -Arishta* (Hydro-alcoholic preparation), *Sneha Kalpana* (fat preparation) etc. are considered as secondary preparations. *Ghrita Kalpana* (Ghee preparation) is one among secondary ayurvedic dosage form explained under the heading of *Sneha Kalpana* in classical texts.

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Sneha kalpas manufactured in ayurvedic pharmaceuticals are used extensively for medicinal as well as cosmetic purpose. It is one of the widely used preparation in ayurvedic drug industry to achieve solubility of both fat soluble and water-soluble extractives into the oil medium.

सर्पिस्तैलं वसा मज्जा सर्वस्नेहोत्तमा मतः ।

एषु चैवोत्तमं सर्पिः संस्कारस्यानुवर्तनात् ॥³

च.सू.13/13

Ghrita, Taila, Vasa, Majja are the *Sneha dravyas* of all. Amongst them *Ghrita* is the best *Sneha dravya* parexcellance because it has “*Sanskarasya Anuvartnat*” Guna. It absorbed in all *Sukshma strotas* of the body.

Dhanyaka Ghrita is the important formulation which is mentioned in *Vangasen Samhita*. It is prepared with *Goghrita* by adding *kalka* of the *dhanyaka* and water.

धान्यकं तुवरं स्निग्धमवृष्यं मूत्रलं लघु ।

तिक्त कटुष्णवीर्यश्च दीपनं पाचनं स्मृतं ॥

ज्वरघ्नं रोचकं ग्राही स्वादुपाकी त्रिदोषनुत् ।

तृष्णादाहवमिशवासकासकार्श्यक्रिमीप्रणुत् ।

आर्द्रन्तु तद् गुणं स्वादु विशेषात्पित्तनाशनम् ॥⁴

भा.प्र.नि.1/87,88

Dhanyaka is used in many diseases in Ayurveda like *Jwara, Trishna, Kasa, Shwasa, Chhardi, Daha, Karshya, Krimi* etc. *Dhanyaka* also *Tridoshaghna, Grahi* and having *Deepan, Pachana* properties.

2. Material and method:

Three essential components required for the preparation of *Snehakalpana*.

कल्काच्चतुर्गुणीकृत्यं घृतं वा तैलमेव वा ।

चतुर्गुणे द्रवे साध्यं तस्य मात्रा पलोन्मिता ॥⁵

शा.सं.मं.खं.9/1

1.Kalka dravya(a fine paste of the one drug or mixture of drugs) - 1 part

2. Sneha dravya - 4 parts

3. Drava dravya (a liquid which may be one or more as Kashaya, Swaras, Dugdha, Water etc.) – 16 parts

In *Dhanyaka Ghrita paka, Goghrita* is taken and heated on *Mandagni*, then prepared *Kalka* is added to it. then water is added and whole contents are boiled together till the water portion get evaporated and *ghrita* becomes free from froth and till *Sneha Siddhi Lakshanas* are obtain.

There is confirmation test for completion of *Sneha paka* ⁶–

1. Sneha kalka attains perfect wick-like shape when rolled between thumb and index finger.
2. Sneha kalka is put into the fire, no sound is produced indicating the loss of moisture in it.
3. Disappearance of bubbles in Ghrita and appearance of bubbles in taila.
4. Appearance of gandha, varna and rasa varies from one formulation to formulation.

2.1. Composition of Dhanyaka Ghrita:

2.1.1. *Dhanyaka*⁴ - (Reference – Bhavprakash Nighantu 1/87,88)

Botanical name - *Coriandrum sativum* Linn.

Family - Umbellifereae

Vernacular name - English - Coriander fruit

Hindi - Dhaniya

Marathi - Dhane

Rasa - *Kashaya, Tikta, Katu*

Guna - *Snigdha, Laghu*

Veerya - *Ushna*

Vipaka - *Madhura*

Karmas - *Deepan, Pachana, Grahi, Tridoshashamaka, Mutral, Hridya, Chakshushya.*

2.1.2. *Goghrita*⁷ –

शस्तं धीस्मृतिमेधाग्निबलायुः शुक्रचक्षुषाम् ।

बालवृद्धप्रजाकांतिसौकुमर्यस्थिराथिनाम् ॥

क्षतक्षीणपरीसर्पशस्त्राग्निग्लपित्तात्मनाम् ।

विपाके मधुरं शीतं वातपित्तविषापहम् ।

चक्षुष्यं बल्यमग्र्यश्च गत्यं सर्पिगुणोत्तरम् ॥

ध.नि.6/135-136

Rasa - *Madhura*

Guna - *Mrudu, Snigdha, Guru*

Veerya - *Sheeta*

Vipaka – *Madhura*

Karmas – *Agnivardhaka, Dhi-dhruiti-smruti vardhaka, Vrushya, Chakshushya, Vishahara, Kantivardhaka, Swarya, Vayasthapana*

Doshaghnta – *Vata-pitta shamak*

(According to Harita Samhita 8/77 – Tridosahara⁸)

Indications⁹ – *Udavarta, Unmada, Apasmara, Shoola, Jwara, Anaha etc.*

(उदावर्तोन्मादापस्मारशूलज्वारानाहवातपित्तप्रशमनमग्निदीपनम् | - सु.सू.45/96)

2.2. References of Dhanyaka Ghrita

1. धान्यकल्केन संसिद्ध चतुर्गुणेजले घृतम् |

पित्तातिसारे सरूजे देयं दीपनपाचनम् ||¹⁰

वं.से.10/91(अतिसाराधिकार)

Kalka dravya - Dhanyaka kalka

Sneha dravya - Goghrita

Drava dravya - Jala

Indications - Atisara specially pittaja atisarajanya shoola, Deepan, Pachana.

2. धान्यजीरकसंसिद्धम् घृतमग्निवर्धनम् |

रोचनं दोषशमनं छर्दीदाहविनाशनम् ||¹¹

वं.से.38/107(अजीर्णाधिकार)

Kalka dravya - Dhanyaka and Jeeraka kalka

Sneha dravya - Goghrita

Drava dravya - Jala

Indications - Agnivardhaka, Ruchikara, Tridosha-shamaka, Chhardi, Daha-shamaka.

3. धान्यकं निस्तुषं कृत्वा जले चाष्टगुणे पचेत् |

तेन् पादावशेषेण तत्कल्कैर्विपचेद्धतम् |

वातरोगेषु सर्वेषु पैतिकेषु च शस्यते |

कफजेषु च रोगेषु सर्पिरेतद्यथामृतम् ||¹²

वं.से.38/108-109(अजीर्णाधिकार)

Kalka dravya - Dhanyaka kalka

Sneha dravya - Goghrita

Drava dravya - Dhanyaka kwatha

Indications - Sarva Vataja, Pittaja, Kaphaja rogas.

4. धान्यकस्य तु शुद्धस्य चतुःषष्टीपलानि च ।

जलद्रोणे विप्लवक्तव्यं यावत्पादावशेषितम् ॥

घृप्रस्थं पचेतेन शनैर्मृद्वगनी भिषक ।

जीरकस्य पलान्यष्टौ कल्कीकृत्य निधापयेत् ।

अग्निसन्दीपनं गुदे शूलं शूलं वंक्षणयोनिजम् ॥¹³

वं.से.38/112-114 (अजीर्णाधिकार)

Kalka dravya - Jeeraka kalka

Sneha dravya - Goghrita

Drava dravya - Dhanyaka kwatha

Indications – Agnideepaka, Hridya, Kaphanashaka, Amshoola, Gudashoola, Vankshanashoola, Yonishoola, Udavarta, Arsharoga.

3. Discussion

The references of *Dhanyaka Ghrita* are found in *Vangasen Samhita*. It is commonly indicated in *Atisara* specially *pittaja Atisarajanya shoola*, *Ajirna*, *Amvata*, *Amashoola*, *Yonishoola*, *Chhardi*, *Daha*, *Trishna*, *Sarva Vataja-Pittaja-Kaphaja Rogas*.

Atisara, *Ajirna* etc. these are the common diseases in clinical practice. In this specially *Atisara* (Diarrhea) finds a place as important disease in individuals life time. Most important factor in the pathogenesis of disease is *Mandagni*. According to Ayurveda, main cause of disease is *Agnimandya*¹⁴. *Agnidosha* and *Ajirna* contribute significantly towards the disease pathogenesis. It is root cause of *Amadosha* and it is crucial factor for manifestation of most of the diseases including *Atisara*. *Amadosha* results due to *Agnidushti* caused by *mityaaharavihara*, ultimately manifesting as *Atisara*. In short, *Mandagni* is the most important factor in causation of diseases. Therefore, drugs used for treatment should act directly or indirectly on *Agni*. In such a condition, *Dhanyaka Ghrita* play important role because *Dhanyaka* possess *Deepana*, *Pachana*, *Pittaghna* and *Grahi* properties.

There are four references of *Dhanyaka Ghrita* given in *Vangasen Samhita*. From this –

- The Reference from V.S.10/91 (*Atisaradhikara*) where *Dhanyaka* is used as *kalka dravya*, *Goghrita* as *Sneha dravya* and *Jala* as *drava dravya*, this formulation is indicated in *Atisara* specially *Pittaja Atisarajanya shoola* and it has *Deepana* and *Pachana* properties.
- The Reference V.S.38/107 (*Ajirnadhikara*) in which *Dhanyaka* and *Jeeraka* are used as *kalka dravya*, *Goghrita* as *Sneha dravya* and *Jala* is used as *Drava dravya*. This formulation acts as a *Tridosha-shamaka*, *Daha shamaka*, *Agnivardhaka*, *Ruchikara* and *Chardighna*. In *Vangasen Samhita*, this formulation is named as *Dhanyajeeraka ghrita* and in *Bharat Bhaishajya Ratnakar*¹⁵, this formulation is named as *Dhanyadi Ghrita*.
- The reference V.S.38/108-109 (*Ajirnadhikara*) *Dhanyaka* is used as *kalka dravya*, *Goghrita* as *Sneha dravya*, *Dhanyaka kwatha* as *drava dravya*, and this formulation is indicated in *Sarva Vataja*, *Pittaja* and *Kaphaja rogas*.
- The Reference V.S.38/112-114 (*Ajirnadhikara*) *Jeeraka* is used as *kalka dravya*, *Goghrita* as *Sneha dravya*, *Dhanyaka kwatha* as *drava dravya*, and this formulation is indicated in *Amashoola*, *Gudashoola*, *Vankshanashoola*, *Yonishoola*, *Udavarta*, *Arsharoga*. It is also *Agnivardhaka*, *Kapha-shamaka* and *Hridya*.

4. Conclusion

Dhanyaka Ghrita is the reference available in *Vangasen Samhita* in *Atisaradhikara* and *Ajirnadhikara*. *Atisara* and *Ajirna* are the common diseases in clinical practice, and main cause of disease is *Agnimandya*. *Agnidosha* and *Ajirna* contribute

significantly towards the disease pathogenesis. So, drugs used in treatment should acts on Agni. In such a condition, Dhanyaka play important role because it possesses Deepana, Pachana and Grahi properties, dhanyaka is also Tridosha-shamaka.

The ingredients of Dhanyaka Ghrita are available in market. So, chances of adulteration are also less. This formulation is easy to prepare but not easily available in market as it is not much prescribed by physicians.

It is necessary to explore the therapeutics of this formulation for betterment of the mankind. And hence various clinical, experimental studies need to be carried out to prove its efficacy.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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